

Keywords:

#Environment, #EnvironmentalIndicators, #Dashboard, #ClimateChange, #ENVRIFAIR, #ResearchCommunity, #EOSCinPractice, #ENVRI

Dashboard for the State of the Environment

A European Dashboard showcasing the State of the Environment

The Project Involved

The Dashboard for the State of the Environment is developed by the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRIs) as one of the Science Projects of the EOSC Future, using the experience and results of the ENVRI-FAIR project. The ENVRI Dashboard aims to make European environmental data accessible to a broad audience through user-oriented indicators displayed in an easy-to-approach interface. The overarching goal of the project is to equip the broader public and policymakers with a user-friendly, customisable dashboard that visualises an extensible collection of indicators that describe the state of the environment in near real-time.

The User Community

The Environmental Research Infrastructure (ENVRI) community is a cluster of European research infrastructures focused on the environment and Earth system science. The ENVRI-FAIR project which concluded in June 2023 aimed to advance the FAIRness of their data and services with emphasis on their interoperability and connect the ENVRI community to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Angeliki Adamaki

EU Project Manager
ICOS Carbon Portal, Lund University

"The Dashboard's central service is designed and built on a fully open-source foundation, and it embodies a flexible and scalable system, reflecting the core concept. As a result, we encourage other Research Infrastructures and EOSC providers to adopt this service as an additional platform for sharing their data and services with a wider audience."

The Challenge

The project set out to find a solution for providing information on the state of the environment displaying multi-disciplinary data from multiple sources in a coherent and user-oriented interface. The developing teams had to create interchangeable and rearrangeable frames, each carrying its own customisation menu. When logged in, user preferences need to be saved for easier and faster access to the preferred data and services, allowing the users to configure their own Dashboard with the indicators of their interest.

The solution

The Science Project demonstrates how different services and multi-disciplinary data resources from multiple research groups can be combined and used to generate scientifically justified environmental indicators in an easy way. The components make use of existing RI services that are onboarded to EOSC, while the new Dashboard service components are integrated in the EOSC for wider access and possible re-use by other research groups. Moreover, several EOSC core services are used, including the EOSC AAI federation, the monitoring service and the EOSC Helpdesk.

The project aims to:

1. develop and launch a dashboard for environmental indicators by setting up analytical workflows for different environmental disciplines and integrating their outputs;
2. connect the analytical frameworks to the Dashboard service and integrate them in the EOSC platform;
3. mobilise and empower larger scientific communities engaging them as providers, co-creators and end-users;
4. demonstrate and promote the benefits and potential of web-based science using EOSC

Keywords:

#Environment, #EnvironmentalIndicators, #Dashboard, #ClimateChange, #ENVRIFAIR, #ResearchCommunity, #EOSCinPractice, #ENVRI

Benefits and impact

The Dashboard for the State of the Environment is a powerful tool that gathers a significant trove of European environmental data in one location. The simplicity of the interface lowers the threshold for non-specialists and citizen scientists to access the data. At the same time, higher-end technical possibilities offer additional options for more advanced users. The Dashboard can serve both scientists and the public by giving access to environmental data and services that are developed at the infrastructure level. The ENVRI services will be developed further within the EOSC environment and the user communities will continue growing. The impact of the project can be seen at strategic, scientific and policy level.

The Dashboard is designed to be completely user configurable so that the users can select from a list the indicators to be shown and their order. Providers can add, remove and edit indicators through a standard REST API, that allows transferring all parameters, including the configuration of the indicators and how to provision data values and thumbnail interaction. The Dashboard is implemented and operated using engineering best practices, including YAML for the indicators' descriptions and a robust and flexible container-based deployment.

Why do I need EOSC?

Through EOSC Future, the Dashboard has been developed using several EOSC services available on the EOSC Platform. As an integration platform that supports scientific workflows, the EOSC provides core services to support research infrastructures to further develop or improve their services, which are also onboarded on the EOSC Platform, and become available to all EOSC users.

The Dashboard is part of the ENVRI-Hub architecture, a common virtual interface for ENVRI-FAIR data and services that can be integrated into higher level platforms as is the EOSC, enabling users from a broader scope to easily access the available data and services.

Useful material related to this story

EOSC Future_Data in action

envri.eu

Across disciplines

To showcase the benefits of an integration platform that supports scientific workflows, the ENVRI develop the "Dashboard for the State of the Environment" as a cross-RI and cross-discipline service to address with scientific facts the environmental concerns. The project brings together three scientific domains (Atmosphere, Biodiversity, Ocean) that each have set up analytical workflows to provide environmental indicators (in near-real-time wherever possible), allowing the users to visualise the "State of the Environment" by interacting with the service interface. The Dashboard's strength lies in its universal and flexible nature, capable of expanding continuously with its extensible collection of indicators. Moreover, it allows data providers from other clusters and disciplines to contribute additional social/behavioral data, enriching the user's understanding of the environment's state.

Future developments

This Science Project leverages various EOSC services, including AAI (Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure), cloud services, and data storage. The workflows responsible for generating the environmental indicators also integrate with the EOSC and Research Infrastructure (RI) computing capabilities. As a proof of concept, a limited set of indicators is currently accessible. However, it is anticipated that the participating RIs will contribute a plethora of additional indicator options in the coming times. With the appropriate technologies in place (APIs, metadata templates etc.), new RIs will have the opportunity to join the initiative and contribute their own indicators to the "Dashboard for the State of the Environment."

Liked this
#EOSCinPractice
story?

Follow
@EOSCFuture
for more!

Share your own #EOSCinPractice story here